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Difference Of Learning Progress In Students By Using Chalk-Talk Strategy And Training Aids

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ABSTRACT

In teaching, Chalk-Talk strategy and use of trg aids play vital role for learning of students. To check the difference in both, study was conducted “Difference of learning progress in students by using chalk-talk strategy and training aids”, comprising objectives; to find learning progress in students by using chalk-talk strategy; to find learning progress in students by using training aids; and to find out the difference in both strategies. Researcher used quantitative research approach, experimental research design and convenience sampling method was used. Two sections of a class, A (experimental group) & B (control group) comprising 30 students each were selected for the experiment. Class A was taught through the training aids and Class B was taught through chalk-talk method for 15 days. Pre-test of subject being taught through the period of experiment and post test was conducted after completion the experiment for collection of data. Results of the study show that, progress of learning of students was low in chalk-talk strategy in comparison to training aids. Study recommends that modern training aids may be utilized in educational institutions as the utilization of training aids brought a good impact on the learning progress of students. It was concluded form the experimental study that, use of training aids is more beneficial than the old technique.

Key Words: Training Aids, Learning Progress

Introduction

Teaching- learning process has been started since the start of this world. However after passing of various eras, traditional teaching method was evolved through the generations cognitive development. In recent past, teaching and learning process was carried out through chalk-talk strategy till the decades 80s & 90s. But after the collaboration of various fields with the education field use of training aids was increased. Various studies were conduct to measure the effectiveness of various training aids in comparison to old methods and it was observed that the same are more efficiently performing their role in progress learning of students.

Significant school-related factor influencing pupils' academic progress has been shown to be teachers' effectiveness. Student achievement is directly correlated with teachers' quality in terms of training, expertise, teaching methods, utilization of resources, content delivery and evaluation. It is impossible to overstate the contribution that audio-visual materials make to teaching, learning and academic accomplishment among students.

The effectiveness of using visual teaching tools in the classroom has been demonstrated. However, secondary schools in Pakistan deal with a host of issues that lower student achievement. In most secondary schools in Pakistan, teaching and learning take place in a very unfavorable setting without access to necessary materials, according to Ahmed (2003).

The purpose of the school is to provide for learning and instruction, so it's critical that the facilities are in place for this purpose. To achieve the necessary standard, the education system needs to be modified and reorganized. The resources provided in schools are expected to be related to the educational setting in order to attain the required academic output because research has demonstrated that school facilities have a significant impact on student achievements.

Background of Study

Undoubtedly, one of the most significant components of human life is education, which also serves as a catalyst for change. It is essential for sustaining ongoing growth. Producing the necessary labor force for all economic sectors and preparing students for meaningful living in society are two goals of educational institutions. The purpose of education is to give each student the chance to realize his or her full potential in terms of academic, professional, social-personal and emotional growth (Kauchak, 2011).

Objectives

- i. To find learning progress in students by using chalk-talk strategy.
- ii. To find learning progress in students by using training aids.
- iii. To find out the difference in both strategies

Significance of the Study

In 21st century, where world has become a global village and developed randomly, in our public sector schools still use old techniques of teaching. Literacy rate of our country is at very low after independence of 76 years. Therefore, researcher decided to carry out a research on "Difference of learning progress in students by using chalk-talk strategy and training aids". This study will significantly beneficial for the authorities to coup up the modern teaching strategies being used in all over the world and to improve the learning progress in students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training aids seek attention of students and it becomes easy for teachers to convey their message for understanding and elaborating concepts. Training aids support teaching and learning process easily. According to some notable researchers, definition of training aids have been defined as under.

As defined by Singh, (2005), any appliance which increase the utilization effect in learning more than earlier utilization of that appliance through AV equipments.

As defined by Singh, (2005), a demonstration which is understandable to the senses of a normal person is learning and learning equipments which can be easily acceptable (Singh, 2005).

According to Agun et al., (1977), gadgets related to instructional nature i.e. auditory, optical and a varied natures which are used as material for teaching and learning purpose.

According to Rather, (2004), optical training gadgets are instructional equipment utilized in schools to foster learning, making easier to comprehend and for making education much fascinating. Other training facilities like, paper strips, paper charts, replicas, viewgraphs, transistor, TV are some of the instances which are related as learning and teaching aids.

Use of training assisting items is beneficial in a way that, whole class is capable to see any educational illustration i.e. audio, video or any other training aid assisted equipment.

During the teaching practices, at the time of using colours have a heavy distinction and looks obvious. Usefulness of training aid items can be enhanced by use of accurate placing, sequencing to elaborate previous information.

The term "AV Aids" or "learning resources" refers to the tools that are utilized in the classroom to promote all educational programmes and make them more efficient, entertaining and simple (Iqbal, 2005). According to a study, major difference in the achievement of academic excellence was observed between pupils who used visual aids in the classroom and those who departed without them. Instead of those who received the lesson without the correct A/V aids, those who were taught in class with them received great grades on the yearly exam (Ellington, 1993).

The majority of less developed nations in the world, like Pakistan, do not utilize instructional materials adequately over the whole instructional term. They discovered that there are several factors that contribute to the inappropriate and overuse of these materials. Additionally, they said that the educational quality is quite poor owing to a lack of instructional resources, which prevents pupils from receiving good marks and negatively impacts their academic achievement, particularly at the secondary school level. Additionally, it was claimed that teachers in less underdeveloped nations lack the necessary skills for using these tools effectively. Today's instructional programmes are made simple, engaging and successful by contemporary technology like multimedia, projectors and computers (Sulaiman, et al., 2012).

Training aids are very helpful for utilization, in the teaching learning process in the schools, colleges and even in universities. Correct use of the training aids help students to learn actively and keeps in their minds for long time in comparison to use chalk-talk strategy. Further it is also necessary to use these training aids properly, otherwise, it will not be effective, loss of time/ resources and cause de-motivation. It has also been observed that, those pupils were taught using training aids during teaching, secured good grades in the academics results. Using training aids in a beneficial way will certainly improve students understanding and

in clearance of concepts of complex or even easy things and teaching learning process will be interesting (Breht, 2012).

Teachers perspectives for the utilization of modern gadgets and training aids i.e. projector, animation videos, films, images and all other related material is positive and inspiring. Both the instructors and the kids from private and public schools were chosen. The majority of respondents to this survey expressed satisfaction with the use of educational tools in classrooms (Shabira Lyni et al., 2015).

METHODOLOGY

Researcher used quantitative research approach and experimental research design was selected. Population of the study consisted all secondary schools in Tehsil Lawa, with a sample of 60 students of class 7th from one secondary school. Convenience sampling technique was used. Two sections of a class, A & B were selected for the experiment. Each class was comprised a group of thirty (30) pupils and total number of sample was sixty (60) pupils. One Section (A) was treated as the experimental group, and other section (B) was considered as control group. Class A was taught through the training aids and Class B was taught through chalk-talk method for 15 days by the teacher i.e. Researcher. Both groups were conducted pre-test of subject being taught through the period of experiment and post test was conducted after completion the experiment.

Research Design

In this research, experimental research design was used. Study comprised of two groups, which were experimental and control group.

Population of the Study

In this study, population was all schools of Tehsil Lawa at secondary level. However, out of the total population of the study under consideration, sample was chosen from the students of elementary stage of the academic session during the year 2022. According to the estimation, size of total population was 2749 students. Details of students was as under:-

a.	Students in 6 th Class	-	978
b.	Students in 7 th Class	-	976
c.	Students in 8 th Class	-	796

Sampling

Researcher randomly selected one school from the population as sample which was, Government High School -2 located at Dhurnal, Tehsil,Lawa. Class seven was chosen and 2x sections of that class were earmarked for the research by using convenience sampling technique. Out of total 60 students, class was divided in two sections A& B, having 30 students each. Section A was selected for

experimental group whereas other section B was selected for control group.

Research Instrument

Teacher made test of history subject was used as the instrument by the researcher. Test was prepared having MCQs, short questions, filling the blanks and match column test. Both the groups were administered tests.

Data Collection

Data was acquired through post-tests. The research instrument used was a teacher-made achievement test. The achievement exam included demographic information and MCQs (multiple-choice questions), filling the blanks and short answer question.

Data Analysis

Collected data was entered into SPSS to analyze the objectives of the study. Results of the study were obtained by using independent sample t-test and Paired sample t-test. The method for data analysis for the scores of achievement tests conducted was descriptive statistics (percentage)..

RESULT

Table 1

Statistics of Age (control and experimental group)

Age	Freq	Percent	Cumulative %
11	12	20.0	20.0
12	19	31.7	51.7
13	29	48.3	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Table 2

Numbers in MCQs students obtained

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
0	1	1.7	1.7
1	1	1.7	3.3
2	10	16.7	20.0
3	8	13.3	33.3
4	27	45.0	45.0
5	33	55.0	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Table 3

Numbers in SQs students obtained in cntrol and experimental group

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
0	1	1.7	1.7

2	7	11.7	13.3
4	13	21.7	35.0
6	7	11.7	46.7
8	23	38.3	85.0
10	8	13.3	98.3
6	1	1.7	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Table 4
Numbers in blanks students in control and experimental group

	Freq	Percent	Cumulative %
1	1	1.7	1.7
2	6	10.0	11.7
3	11	18.3	30.0
4	24	40.0	70.0
5	18	30.0	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Table 5
Numbers in columns students in control and experimental group

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
0	1	1.7	1.7
1	5	8.3	10.0
2	10	16.7	26.7
3	6	10.0	36.7
5	38	63.3	100.0
Total	60	100.0	

Table 6

Overall statistics of numbers obtained (control and experimental group)

Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
8	13.5	13.4
17	28.1	41.5
30	50.1	91.9
5	8.2	100.0
60	100.0	

Table 7
Group statistics of t-Test (control & experimental group)

	Cr & Ex group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Std. Er M
Age	Ex group A	30	2.17	.791	.145
	Cr group B	30	2.40	.770	.141
MCQs	Ex group A	30	4.93	.254	.046
	Cr group B	30	3.00	1.287	.235
SQs	Ex group A	30	4.17	.592	.108
	Cr group B	30	2.23	1.251	.228
Blanks	Ex group A	30	4.53	.629	.115
	Cr group B	30	3.20	.887	.162
Colum	Ex group A	30	4.87	.507	.093
	Cr group B	30	2.90	1.647	.301
Total Marks	Ex group A	30	4.17	.379	.069
	Cr group B	30	2.90	.662	.121

Findings

In the light of objective 1, it was found that learning progress of students is sufficient who were taught using chalk-talk strategy. Findings of objective 2 indicate that results of students who were taught through using training aids are high than the other group. Furthermore, there is a significant and huge difference in the progress in comparison to both the technique as found in objective 3.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the use of training aids has a significant effect on the learning progress of students. The study found that the use of training aids has improved the leaning progress and comprehension among students compared to the traditional chalk-talk method. The experiment group, which used training aids, showed a significantly high scores in tests than the control group. Results highlight the importance of incorporating training aids in teaching to enhance students' learning process.

Recommendation

1. It is recommended that, authorities may allocate funds and resources for the provision of training aids to schools.
2. Teachers should use the available training aids for the improved and better learning progress of students.
3. The focus of all such type of initiatives and projects may be for the instructional methods and techniques necessary for effective emerging training equipment and existing teaching methods keeping in view the limited resources.
4. To improve the students leaning capability schools should made a balance availability of training aids in addition to chalkboards, books and maps.
5. Teachers should also be educated to use training aids and awareness is needed to be increased among teachers to improve their subject knowledge and teaching methods.

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